

Scheduling Home Appliances to Optimize Energy Consumption

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Abstract

- Energy demand peaks should be avoided
- Energy consumption should be distributed in time in order to consume electricity more efficiently
- Set maximum energy consumption per household to avoid demand peaks
- We present a theoretical model of how to use teletraffic theory for house environments to analyze performance when there is a energy consumption limit

Approach

- Use teletraffic theory and queuing theory to study performance of the scheduling
- Teletraffic theory studies network performance: average waiting time in the queue, the expected number waiting or receiving service, blocking probability, etc.
- Queuing theory is the mathematical study of waiting lines, or queues. The theory permits the derivation and calculation of several performance measures.
- We present a theoretical model of how to use teletraffic theory for house environments to analyze performance when there is a energy consumption limit
- We define our system as a multi-dimensional loss-delay system with preemptive resume queuing and Poisson arrival rates.

Theoretical Background

- *Poisson distribution*: is a discrete probability distribution that expresses the probability of a number of events occurring in a fixed period of time if these events occur with a known average rate and independently of the time since the last event.
- *Multi-dimensional loss-delay systems*: is a system which has several traffic streams with different bandwidth demand offered to the same group of channels.
- *Preemptive queuing system*: is a queuing system where services can be interrupted by new arriving service if this arriving service has higher priority than the service being served.
- *Preemptive resume*: the interrupted service is continued from where it was interrupted.

Home Appliances Priorities

- We have divided home appliances into three main priority classes:
 - *Active appliances*: are the appliances turned on by the user which should not be blocked or delayed as this will have a negative impact for the user. Example: TV, computer, lights, microwave, etc.
 - *Secondary appliances*: are the appliances that can be delayed, as they won't affect users' comfort. Example: washing machine, air conditioner, dryer, dishwasher, recharging battery, etc.
 - *Stand-by appliances*: are the appliances that are draining electricity but are not being used. Example: TV and DVD player in stand-by, lights (in rooms where there is no user), etc.
- In our system active appliances have the highest priority and stand-by appliances have the lowest priority.

Event Driven Scheduling Algorithm

Example Scenario

1. The user turns on the washing machine, which starts consuming power
2. The user starts vacuuming. As the maximum wattage is 1000 W, the washing machine is interrupted.
3. The fridge needs to cool down, this task is queued until available voltage.
4. The users stops vacuuming. The washing machine can continue and the fridge can start.
5. The fridge is back to its ideal temperature
6. The user makes a coffee, the washing machine is paused again
7. The user turns on the TV
8. The coffee is ready. The washing machine can continue

Conclusions

- We try to give an overview of how we can apply well established teletraffic theories into energy efficiency
- Scheduling appliances consumption can help avoid demand peaks
- Utilities can reward users who consume energy more uniformly, ex. cheaper prices
- Possible problems: the user wants to activate too many active appliances at once. Then the consumption limit can be exceeded and the user has to pay more

Further Work

- The work presented in this project is just an initial approach to use teletraffic theory to control energy usage.
- This work opens the window to use well accepted and validated teletraffic theories to energy management.